

CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIVEMENT

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION
FOR ACTIVELY PARTICIPATING IN THE JOURNAL

Юлдашев Акмал Ахмаджонович

**G. HIRSUTUM L. ТУРИНИНГ ДУРАГАЙЛАРИДА ГЕНЛАРНИНГ ЎЗАРО ТАЪСИРИ
НАТИЖАСИДА ПОЯНИ ЎСИШ ТИПЛАРИНИНГ ИРСИЙЛАНИШИ**

WILL BE AWARDED FOR THEIR PARTICIPATION IN THE ARTICLE

